

A fertility-restoring revertant, controlled by a single gene induced from a rice cytoplasmic male sterile line

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Cytoplasmic male sterility is inherited steadily through the maternal parent. However, reversions of cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines to male fertile lines, either by cytoplasmic or nuclear gene mutation, have been documented (Nawa et al 1987, Smith 1987, He et al 1989). We report a fertility-restoring revertant induced from an indica rice CMS line II-32A treated with γ -rays, which is perhaps the first case in rice.

Dry seeds (13% moisture) of CMS rice line II-32A, which possesses the cytoplasm of an Indonesian rice variety, were irradiated with ^{60}Co - γ rays at a dose of 290 Gy. Eight plants with an open air seed-setting rate of more than 30% were selected from about 1,000 M_1 II-32A individuals planted in an isolated area. These plants showed segregation in later generations. Among them, line T24 segregated for completely sterile and fully fertile plants. The sterile plants had 100% pollen grains that were shrunken and not stainable with I_2 -KI. The fertile plants had a seed-setting rate of about

80% in the open air and more than 90% dark-stained pollen grains.

In the 1993 early season, revertant T24 line was testcrossed with Zhenshan 97 A and II-32 A for its fertility-restoring ability. The results were grouped into two sets. In set one, both the parental T24 and the F_1 plants were fertile. In set two, the parental T24 plants segregated into a 3 fertile-1 sterile ratio. F_1 plants showed a 1 fertile-1 sterile ratio, indicating that the revertant could restore the fertility of CMS lines and one pair of nuclear genes of T24 might control the restoring ability.

To clarify the above facts, the seed-setting rate distribution in F_2s of the crosses between II-32 A, Zhenshan 97 A, DShan A, Xieqinza A, and T24 were investigated in the 1993 late season in Hangzhou and in the 1994 early season in Hainan Island. The F_2 seed-setting rate distributions of all four crosses were clearly divided into sterility (0-40%) and fertility (70-100%). The supplemental pollen vigor assay with I_2 -KI revealed the pollen grains of the sterile plants in the open air to be completely abortive, the seed setting of which resulted from cross pollination.

The ratio of the fertile plants to sterile ones in F_2s of the four crosses was 3:1 ($\chi^2 = 1.12, 0.20 < p > 0.30$ for II-32 A/T24, $\chi^2 = 0.2735, 0.50 < p > 0.70$ for Zhenshan 97 A/T24, $\chi^2 = 0.003, p > 0.99$ for DShan A, $\chi^2 = 0.1077, p = 0.30$ for Xieqinza A/T24). The genetic mode of the fertility-restoring ability of T24 was different from that of Minghui 63 and 20964, the leading

restorers in southern China (see table). The bagged seed-setting rate and the seed-setting rate in open air of II-32 A/20964 and II-32A/Minghui 63 were widely distributed. The fertility-restoring ability possessed by 20964 and Minghui 63 was thought to be controlled by two pairs of nuclear genes, based on the proportion of sterile individuals to total segregating F_2 plants.

The fertility-restoring revertant created in this study is of significance because first, the reversion process inferred that rice CMS is not as complicated as previously thought (conditioned by the incompatibility between cytoplasm and nucleus). The revertant, still possessing sterile cytoplasm, provides not only a restoring gene source, but also a restorer selection system. The revertant also provides excellent material for CMS molecular studies.

Cited References

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Distribution of F_2 seed-setting rate for crosses of T24 with indica CMS rice lines.

Cross combination ^b	Seed-setting rate distribution ^a											χ^2 (3:1)	P
	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100		
IIA/T24		16	12	5	1			8	16	25	45	1.1200	0.20-0.30
ZSA/T24		13	11	2			3	2	3	21	42	0.2735	0.50-0.70
DSA/T24		19	3				5	6	7	21	30	0.0003	>0.99
XQZA/T24		18	4	3			3	3	11	18	33	0.1077	0.3
IIA/MH63	3	6	6	9	9	10	9	3	1	1		$k = (\log N - \log M) / 0.6021^c$	
IIA/20964	3	6	10	7	7	18	17	7	3				

^a Data for IIA/MH63 and IIA/20964 are bagged seed-setting rate while others are seed-setting rate in open air. ^b ZSA = Zhenshan 97 A, DSA = DShan A, XQZA = Xieqinza A, MH63 = Minghui 63. ^c The number of restoring genes in MH63 and 20964 were estimated with this formula.